

ASP 693 CHEERS

“Cultural HERitagE. Risks and Securing activities”

Deliverable D.T2.2.1 Knowledge base on geo-spatial catalogues of cultural heritage in the Alpine area (country contribution)

Existing approaches for cataloguing cultural assets and archives are collected and analysed for preliminary evaluations on their possible integration at Alpine scale

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List of acronyms

- ADAB - Inventory of combat and conduct works worthy of conservation
- CBC - Cultural Heritage Commission (Commissione dei Beni Culturali)
- DDPS - Federal Department of Defence, Civil Protection and Sport
- EGID - unique object numbers (numeri univoci degli oggetti)
- FOCP - Federal Office of Civil Protection
- FOEN - Federal Office for the Environment
- HOBIM - Inventory of military buildings with architectural value
- IKFÖB - Inventory of combat and conduct works with ecological value or potential
- IFP - Federal Inventory of Landscapes and Natural Monuments
- ISOS - Federal Inventory of Swiss Heritage Sites
- IVS - Inventory of historic traffic routes in Switzerland
- LPBC, 1966 - Federal Cultural Property Protection Act
- LPBC, 2014 - Federal Act on the Protection of Cultural Property in the event of armed conflicts, disasters and emergency situations
- LPN – Federal Act on the Protection of Nature and Cultural Heritage (Legge federale sulla protezione della natura e del paesaggio)
- LPPC - Federal Law on Civil Protection System and Protection & Support Service, 4 October 2002 (Legge federale sulla protezione della popolazione e sulla protezione civile)
- MA - Cantonal Art Museum (Museo cantonale d'Arte)
- OPBC Ordinance on the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflicts, Disasters and Emergencies (Ordinanza sulla protezione dei beni culturali in caso di conflitti armati, catastrofi e situazioni d'emergenza)
- OPVS - Ordinance on the Federal Inventory of Historic Swiss Traffic Routes (Ordinanza riguardante l'inventario federale delle vie di comunicazione storiche della Svizzera)
- OSMA - Swiss Society for Art Monuments (Opera svizzera dei monumenti d'arte)
- PCP - Protection of Cultural Property
- PCI - Civil Protection Regions
- REA - Swiss Federal Register of Buildings and Dwellings (Registro federale svizzero degli edifici e delle abitazioni)
- USTRA - Federal Roads Office (Ufficio federale delle strade)
- SSAS - Society for Art History in Switzerland
- SIBC - Cultural Heritage Information System
- UBC - Office for Cultural Heritage (Ufficio dei beni culturali)

Introduction

As part of activity 2.2, a research was carried out on the available catalogues of cultural assets in Switzerland, addressing both the national level and the regional level of Canton Ticino. The activity describes the system of cultural property protection in Switzerland and in Canton Ticino and it surveys the national and regional inventories considered of interest in the context of this project, addressing the list of cultural heritage, sites and monuments to protect in case of natural catastrophe.

The Protection of Cultural Heritage in Switzerland

The protection of cultural properties in Switzerland is based on two international treaties:

- the *Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict* (1954), the first international treaty to protect cultural heritage after the numerous disruption caused by World War II.
- the *Second Protocol of the Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict* (1999) released after the Balcan's wars and complementing the first treaty by defining the basic responsibilities of States Parties and new higher level of protection of cultural heritage.

The convention is currently ratified by 133 member states¹.

Switzerland ratified the Hague Convention in 1962, setting up a federal structure for the “Protection of Cultural Property” (PCP), with the aim to safeguard, protect and respect Switzerland's cultural heritage for future generations in accordance with the fundamental principles enshrined in the 1954 Hague Convention. The ratification of the conventions implied its concrete adoption through the Federal Cultural Property Protection Act (LPBC) of 6 october 1966.

In 1968, the confederation created a new advisory body: the Swiss Commission for the Protection of Cultural Property, responsible for the drafting and updating the Swiss inventory of properties of national importance, an instrument from which depend the measures to protect and support heritage. The Swiss Commission for the Protection of Cultural Heritage has also ensured continuity in the conception and methodologies of work in the passage of the PCP from the Federal Office of Culture to the Federal Office of Civil Protection.

¹ List of states that have ratified the convention : <https://pax.unesco.org/la/convention.asp?KO=13637&language=E>

The “Protection of Cultural Property” section (PCP) is actually managed by the Federal Office of Civil Protection (FOCP) of the Federal Department of Defence, Civil Protection and Sport (DDPS), acting as a contact body for all questions relating to the Hague Convention and responsible of the compilation and updating of the Swiss Inventory of Cultural Property of National and Regional Significance, in cooperation with the cantons and the Swiss Commission for the Protection of Cultural Property.

From 1962 to 1984 the “Protection of Cultural Property” was managed by Federal Office of Culture of Federal Department of Home Affairs that strongly contributed to drafting the first inventory of cultural heritage, and then passed the direction of the Federal Office of Civil Protection (FOCP) through the Decree of the Federal Cultural Property Protection Act (1984). It is important to highlight this change because, since then, the protection of cultural heritage is led by the Federal Department of Defence, Civil Protection and Sport, adopting a military approach in the protection of cultural properties.

The inventory was compiled in accordance with Article 5 of the Hague Convention, and it has been revised and updated three times over the years (the last has to be confirmed in 2021): it was first drawn up and published in 1988 by the Swiss Commission for the Protection of Cultural Heritage under the Federal Office of Culture. A first revision was published in 1995, while the third update dates back to 2009, following the inclusion of new danger scenarios in the current legislation such as natural disasters, fires and floods² (see chapter below “Swiss Inventory of Cultural Property of National and Regional Significance”).

In 2004, Switzerland signed the Second Protocol of the Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict. Two main changes depend by this agreement:

- 1- the concept of protection has been extended to cover movable collections;
- 2- the focus has shifted from armed conflicts towards natural disasters and other civil emergencies.

Based on this ratification, ten years later, in 2014, Switzerland abrogates the Federal Cultural Property Protection Act (LPBC, 1966) to create a new Federal Act on the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict, Disaster and Emergency Situations³ (LPBC; RS 520.3) and related Ordinance (OPBC: RS 520.31)⁴.

² Federal Law on Civil Protection System and Protection & Support Service, 4 October 2002 (LPPC; RS 520.1)

³ Federal Act on the Protection of Cultural Property Protection Act in the event of armed conflicts, disasters and emergency situations, 20 June 2014 (LPBC; RS 520.3)

⁴ OPBC Ordinance on the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflicts, Disasters and Emergencies, 29 October 2014 (OPBC: RS 520.31)

In addition to the extension of the scenarios to include disasters and emergencies, the new revision of the LPBC introduces the category of "enhanced protection", the application of protective shields to cultural property already in peacetime (Fig. 1 – 2), and the training of specialised staff in cultural institutions (See Box 1 - Training Civil Protection of PCP).

Figura 1 Single shield for marking cultural assets of national importance

Figura 2 Three shields for marking cultural properties under special protection

The related ordinance (OPBC: RS 520.31) defines the categories of cultural property into cultural assets of national importance (object A), regional importance (object B) and local importance (object C) and it specifies also their classification criteria: architectural and artistic importance; scientific importance; ideal and material importance; historical importance; and technical importance. In addition, for buildings, the criteria of importance of the object in the local context or landscape and the quality of the building taking into account its surroundings are equally relevant; for collections, the contextual value, cultural importance and degree of notoriety, and the condition of the objects and how they are stored. The ordinance deliberates the responsibilities of the Federal Office for Civil Protection, the Cantons, the Swiss Commission for the Protection of Cultural Heritage and the Federal Office of Topography Swisstopo, in relation to the setting up of the inventory. Finally it defines the themes to cover with the training of civil protection and cultural institutions staff involved in the cultural property protection.

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Box 1 - Training Civil Protection on the Protection of Cultural Properties (PCP)

In 1975, the Swiss federal government introduced funding regulations and issued clear-cut directives on PCP training and the allocation of responsibilities between the federal authorities and the cantons. Ten years later (1985) three specific PCP training courses were held for the first time to civil protection specialists of the Military Population Protection Section, and since 1992, three 5-day courses have been held each year to train PCP leaders at federal level. At cantonal level instead, since 1993, three 5-day courses have been held every year by each cantons to train civil protection specialists in the protection of cultural properties in emergency situations. These courses cover the following activities: 1) collecting data, 2) handling works of art, 3) preparing protection and evacuation measures, 4) preparing intervention plans; particular emphasis is placed on cataloguing, which is an indispensable basis for any intervention and security measures.

In Canton Ticino, the Office of Cultural Heritage of the Department of the territory is the main consultant of the PCP, it is responsible for cataloguing cultural properties (of national, cantonal and local importance) and for contributing to the training of civil protection specialists in PCP, the drawing up of intervention plans (priorities) and safety documentation. The common objective of this collaboration between the Office of Cultural Heritage and the Civil Protection is to ensure the highest quality both in the preparatory work (training of soldiers; cataloguing) and in the preparation of the operational phases (intervention, protection and evacuation plans).

The Protection of Cultural Heritage in Canton Ticino

In Canton of Ticino, the protection of cultural properties is the responsibility of the Office for Cultural Heritage (Ufficio dei beni culturali, UBC) of the Department of Territory, which works in collaboration with services and bodies in the Canton, the municipalities and cultural institutions. The public services with protection duties are: the Cultural Heritage Commission (Commissione dei Beni Culturali CBC), the Office for Cultural Heritage (UBC), the State Archives, the Cantonal Art Museum (Museo cantonale d'Arte - MA), the Pinacoteca Zust, the Centre for Dialectology and Ethnography, the Logistics Section, the Office for Civil Protection and Integrated Defence.

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In the field of cultural heritage protection, and more specifically in the tasks of cataloguing heritage and preparing protection measures, the Office for Cultural Heritage has been collaborating with the Civil Protection Department for 45 years, since the first Cantonal Law implementing the Federal Law for the Protection of Cultural Heritage (1976)⁵.

The civil protection of the Canton of Ticino is organised into six territorial regions⁶, each of which, every year since 1993, has held training courses for militiamen specialised in the Protection of Cultural Heritage (PCP), during which they are instructed in data collection, the handling of works of art, the preparation of protection and evacuation measures, the preparation of intervention plans and the cataloguing of works, which is indispensable for preparing any intervention and safety measures.

The Cantonal Law on the Protection of Cultural Property (of 13 May 1997) regulates the protection, enhancement and promotion of knowledge of cultural property. It defines the categories of "protected cultural property" - including immovable properties of cantonal and local interest and movable properties belonging to private or public bodies and to recognised cultural institutions - and the responsibilities of each body: the State Council is responsible for active protection and its organisation as a public service, while the owners of the property are responsible for its protection. Chapter 5 regulates in detail the protection of cultural property in the event of armed conflict, and specifies the tasks of the Canton (Art. 41), the characteristics of the inventory (Art. 42-43), and the powers and organisation of the bodies involved (Art. 44-47).

The State Council's duties include appointing a department responsible for taking measures to protect property, drawing up an inventory of the property to be protected, preparing shelters and subsidising communal and private protection measures, organising training for the protection of cultural property for civil protection, and producing security documentation and microfilms on inventoried property. With regard to the characteristics of the inventory, the law stipulates that it must distinguish between assets of cantonal interest and those of local interest, as well as those to be protected in the event of armed conflict or disaster (art. 42), and it includes information sheets on each protected cultural asset (art. 43).

The State Council lays down the methods of collaboration between the various departmental services responsible for the protection of cultural property, while its implementing regulations (2004) set out more specifically the powers and organisation of the services:

- The Office for Cultural Heritage (UBC) decides on the measures to be taken, on the mandate of the Department of Institutions;

⁵ Cantonal law for the application of the federal act for the protection of cultural heritage (1976).

⁶ The six Civil Protection regions in Canton Ticino are: Regione 3 Valli, Regione del Bellinzonese, Regione Locarno e Vallemaggia, Regione di Lugano campagna, Regione di Lugano città, Regione del Mendrisiotto.

- The Office for Civil Protection and Integrated Defence, in collaboration with the UBC, promotes the protection of property, working with the owners of the property and in particular with the Civil Protection Regions (PCI).
- A working group is set up specifically to facilitate collaboration between the services and bodies involved, in which all aspects of education and operations in this field are discussed and coordinated.

The Office for Cultural Heritage (UBC) is divided into three sections - the Inventory Section, the Monuments Section and the Archaeology Section - and is responsible for the census of all movable and immovable cultural property in the canton and for the inventory. While the law (1997) defined the categories of "protected cultural property", the implementing regulations make a distinction between immovable cultural property (buildings, installations, their parts or assemblies, ruins and archaeological sites) and movable cultural property (paintings, books, documents, archaeological finds, utensils and cultural, artistic or decorative objects). This distinction is useful for drawing up the inventory, which is made up of an information sheet for each item, giving: the name of the item, its location, ownership, and a more specific description, including the reason for and extent of protection. Access to the administrative data is not public, and only those legitimately interested (UBC, CMC, Uffici Protezione Civile) can access the system. This is intended to further protect cultural property from theft. Other data, such as the type, location and photographs of the objects, can be accessed and consulted online⁷.

Institutional national scale catalogues

Swiss Inventory of Cultural Property of National and Regional Significance (PBC)

The Swiss Inventory of Cultural Property of National and Regional Importance is the official register of swiss cultural heritage to be protected. The inventory includes movable and immovable cultural properties, such as monuments, collections and archeological sites. They are classified into two groups: those of national value (class A), and those of regional value (class B). Elements of purely local value (class C) are not included in the list, but can be registered separately by the cantonal authorities.

The PBC Inventory is compiled by the Federal Office for Civil Protection (FOCP) in cooperation with the cantons and the Federal Commission for Cultural Property and it is updated periodically. There are currently four editions of the inventory: the first edition in 1988, the second edition in 1995, the third edition in 2009, and the last one to be published in 2021. The 1988 and 1995 versions also include sites and settlements of national importance, including entire cities, squares, and multiple monuments. Both present a breakdown of assets into objects of category A (national

⁷ <https://www4.ti.ch/dt/dstm/sst/ubc/temi/inventario-dei-beni-culturali/consultazione/consultazione/>

importance) and B (cantonal importance). From the 1998 edition to the 1995 edition, the objects of cantonal importance (B) have undergone only minor changes (with the exception of cultural property that was classified as an A object as part of the revision, changes and proposals for new entries in Inventory B submitted by the cantons between 2000 and 2007, and cultural property downgraded to B objects by the committee responsible for the evaluation) and are available on the Confederation's website divided by classification and canton⁸. The 1995 edition of the PCP Inventory was published in the form of a printed catalogue including both A and B objects and as a 1:300,000 topographical map for A objects only.

PCP Inventory 2009

The 2009 edition of the Inventory includes approximately 3,200 objects that are considered to be "cultural assets of national importance" (buildings, collections of archives, libraries and museums, and archaeological sites), but only covers class A objects. The 2021 edition, on the other hand, is primarily concerned with integrating B objects into the Inventory.

The 2009 edition⁹ contains many new features, especially with regard to the methodology used to evaluate and classify objects. A summary of the most important updates includes:

1. The determination of thresholds for the classification of A objects within a reasonable number, in order to allow an accurate choice of objects to be included in the inventory worthy of protection: 2,500 individual buildings, 250 archaeological sites, 150 archival collections, 120 museum collections and 60 library collections.
2. The exclusive survey and evaluation of individual buildings or objects to be marked with the blue shield, rather than settlements, which are difficult to protect in the event of war, and which are already included in other federal inventories.
3. The extended responsibility of cantons in the survey and categorization of A objects, emerging from the lack of a national basis to refer to for the evaluation of the objects
4. The creation of a binding national matrix to evaluate and classify individual objects of national importance according to uniform criteria within categories to allow cross-cantonal comparison¹⁰. The matrix was initially tested and used to evaluate individual buildings within architectural categories, and later adapted for all other cultural objects in the inventory, including collections.
5. The survey, evaluation and inclusion of collections of national importance held in museums, libraries and archives, assessed and classified according to scientific criteria.

⁸ List of objects B in the inventory by canton : <https://www.babs.admin.ch/it/aufgabenbabs/kgs/inventar/b-objekte.html>

⁹ Protection of Cultural Property Section. 30 October 2009. Revision of the Swiss Inventory of Cultural Property of National and Regional Importance (PCP Inventory). Guidance report. Federal Office for Civil Protection (FOCP), Federal Department of Defence, Civil Protection and Sport (DDPS), Swiss Confederation.

¹⁰ The matrix was developed and tested by a working group consisting of members of the Committee and other specialists (from the fields of conservation of historical monuments, protection of settlements and archaeology) commissioned by the Protection of Cultural Heritage and Historical Monuments Section of the Federal Office of Culture and the Protection of Cultural Property Section of the Federal Office for Civil Protection.

6. Archaeological sites and special cases (Swiss lake steamships, mountain railways, funiculars, etc.) have been listed separately in the inventory.

Selection criteria for classifying A objects in the PCP Inventory

Single constructions. The matrix developed for the evaluation and classification of objects provides the following information:

- architectural and artistic quality;
- criteria inherent in the science of art;
- traditional ideals and materials;
- historical criteria;
- technical criteria;
- contextual criteria;
- situational value;
- regional character (criterion which does not by itself determine classification as object A);
- rarity (a criterion that does not by itself determine classification as object A)

The final evaluation also took into account the variety and typicality of the buildings of the different periods from an architectural point of view, including modern buildings built before 1980.

Museum, archive and library collections. With regard to the inventory of museum collections, it was stipulated that at least a quarter of the objects they contain must be of national importance. For the evaluation and classification of the objects in the different categories - archaeology, history, art, natural sciences, special museums, technology and ethnography - the indications given by the Swiss Museum Guide, the Association of Swiss Museums (ASM) and the Swiss representation of ICOM (International Council of Museums) were taken into account. In the case of archive collections, the inclusion of institutions of national and/or equivalent importance in the inventory was given priority. The archives were also classified into different categories to allow a comparative assessment: federal archives, archives at federal and cantonal level, business archives, town and municipal archives, religious archives and special archives. Finally, the "Guide to Historical Library Collections" was used to assess library collections of national importance, from which around 60 collections were recorded, and to classify them in the PCP inventory in four different categories: public libraries (federal, cantonal, municipal, university, etc.), private libraries, religious libraries and special libraries.

Archaeological sites. The inclusion of archaeological sites in the PCP inventory is not new. They were already included in the 1995 revision, but they were hardly catalogued uniformly for all the cantons. The 2009 revision creates a specific category for archaeological sites, clearly differentiating them from single constructions. The cantonal archaeologists have worked together to identify archaeological sites of national importance within their territory and to determine a uniform classification according to the periods they belong to: Palaeolithic, Mesolithic, Neolithic, Bronze

Age, Iron Age, Roman Age, High Middle Ages, Middle Ages and Modern Age. Only sites that lie within an entire archaeological area have been considered. Although the threshold for the inclusion of archaeological sites in the inventory is limited to a total of 250, this has presupposed that those archaeological sites identified and included in the inventory are exemplary for the understanding of Swiss history and identity today.

Particular cases. These are cases that do not belong to single constructions, and are therefore of no particular architectural interest, nor are they part of movable property. Specifically, the particular cases refer to: technological and industrial monuments including Swiss lake steamships, mountain railways, cable cars, funicular railways, rack railways or other means of transport. Quarries, mines and other installations of the mining industry were also listed in the same category.

PCP Inventory 2021

The last revision is scheduled for 2021. Provisional cantonal lists, objects A and B are available on the Confederation's website¹¹. With regard to the third revision of the inventory, the cantons have submitted to the PCP section an updated list of A and B objects for inclusion in the new inventory. From around 3,200 objects of national importance in 2009, the number has risen to 3,420, i.e. a total of around 13,700 objects including B objects. In view of the large number of B objects reported, considerable effort was invested in systematically verifying the data on B objects (coordinates, addresses, etc.)¹², but it was considered unjustified to apply the same evaluation and classification criteria according to the matrices drawn up in 2009. B objects will continue to appear exclusively in list form and published together with A objects (as in 1988 and 1995, but not in 2009). In contrast to B objects, A objects are represented in the federal geoportal (Fig. 3-4), updated once a year, enriched with additional information such as architectural category, photographs, short texts, links to the objects in question (Fig. 5) which are also included in the military systems.

¹¹ National and regional provisional lists (Objects A and B) as of 9.12.2020.

<https://www.babs.admin.ch/it/aufgabenbabs/kgs/inventar/revision-2021.html>

¹² Data on the location of assets of national and regional importance are based on the unique object numbers (EGID) contained in the Swiss Federal Register of Buildings and Dwellings (REA) and are provided by the Federal Statistical Office. For the time being, the REA still mainly lists inhabited buildings, as well as various religious buildings, but the intention is to include other architectural monuments such as fountains, monuments, bridges, castle ruins, etc. in the register and assign an EGID number.

Figura 3 PBC inventory map representing the A objects on the confederation portal. Objects of national importance are marked with a white-blue shield and areal objects (archaeological areas) are marked with a PCP shield surrounded by a blue circle. (<http://map.geo.admin.ch/?topic=kgs>)

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Figura 4 PBC inventory map representing first viewed information about a selected A object: Isole di Brissago

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admin.ch/rest/services/ech/MapServer/ch.babs.kultur ...

Protection of cultural property inventory with objects of national importance (Federal Office for Civil Protection)

Name	Isole, Parco botanico del cantone
Category	A
Type of object	Bauten für Öffentlichkeit, Gewerbe, Handel, Industrie, Tourismus usw. / Botanische Gärten, Gewächshäuser
PCP ref. no	5342
Address	Brissago
Municipality (Former municipality)	Brissago
Coordinates	2700250 / 1109849
Object information:	kgs_05342_gsk-i.pdf kgs_05342_gsk-d.pdf
Further information	Brissago-Inseln
Further information	Wikipedia: Isole di Brissago

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Figura 5 PBC inventory map representing additional information about a selected A object: Isole di Brissago

Other important changes in the latest revision concern:

1. It was decided to give greater importance to archaeological sites, which had been treated very restrictively in 2009 (the threshold of 250 was criticised), taking into account the current state of research, current scientific research priorities and cultural-historical interests. It was decided to include in the category “archaeology” also objects that were initially included in the category “single constructions” or “collections”, including gallows, castle ruins, mines and military fortifications up to the time of the First World War. In addition, all 56 Swiss pile-dwelling sites on the UNESCO World Heritage List were inscribed as A objects, in line with the art guide of the Society for Art History in Switzerland (SSAS).
2. New criteria for the classification of archives have been determined and numerous downgrades have taken place. The following criteria are determined for the classification of archives as A objects: they must be very significant fonds dating from before 1800 and unique testimonies of the city's history, fonds that have not been handed over to the state archives and cases in which the history of the city is predominantly separate from the history of the canton. The following criteria are decisive for classification as B objects: the fonds must be of supra-local importance and date from before 1800 or have regional significance. Municipal archives proposed by the cantons as new B-objects and business archives set up within the framework of a special mandate are only of municipal importance and are generally not accepted.
3. A reduction in the number of collections was envisaged.
4. The “particular cases” section was abolished. Specifically, some special cases have been downgraded in the cantonal protection lists (e.g. steamships, railways, funiculars and cable cars), while others including quarries, mines and military fortifications have been moved to the Archaeology section.

Federal inventories of national importance

Other inventories of national importance have been created on the basis of Article 5 of the Federal Act of 1 July 1966 on the Protection of Nature and Cultural Heritage (LPN; RS 451), a law aimed at protecting, preserving and maintaining the characteristics of the landscape and the appearance of inhabited areas, as well as the country's natural and cultural monuments (Art. 1 LPN).

These are specifically

- Federal Inventory of Swiss Heritage Sites (ISOS);

- Inventory of historic traffic routes in Switzerland (IVS);
- Federal Inventory of Landscapes and Natural Monuments (IFP).

Federal Inventory of Swiss Heritage Sites (ISOS)

Figura 6 Gandria, ISOS village (2005). Author: Oberpepe. CC-BY-SA
<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Gandria.jpg?uselang=it>

The Federal Inventory of Swiss Settlements of National Importance to be protected (ISOS) is a list of 1274 settlements of national importance defined by the Federal Council, responsible for updating them over the years (survey, modification and deletion) and managed by the Federal Office of Culture following a review with the cantons.

The main objective is to preserve the characteristics that have contributed to the national importance of settlements and to avoid irreversible damage. The ISOS is an indispensable instrument for the protection of monuments and settlements as well as for spatial planning measures relating to settlements of national importance.

The settlements included in the ISOS all have the following characteristics

1. They are included in the first edition of the Siegfried Map.

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2. They have at least ten residential buildings.
3. Their name is recorded in the National Charter.

Settlements are assessed according to the category of agglomeration (city, town, village, etc.) by federal and cantonal experts. The determination of the national interest of a settlement is based on topographical, spatial and historical/architectural criteria. The parameters for surveying settlements allow the inventory to provide information that is comparable and coordinated with other inventories¹³.

The inventory procedure (ISOS method) is based on the current architectural heritage and provides for the attribution of a preservation objective to each settlement. It includes procedures and suggestions for sustainable planning in order not to impede local development and to support municipalities, cantons and the confederation in their decision-making processes. The inclusion of a settlement in the ISOS inventory requires that new buildings and urban extensions take into account the existing and past heritage. In order to ensure the comparability of settlements at the national level, only the external characteristics of the building are included in the ISOS, and not the functional, economic, sociological or political aspects of the settlements, nor the zoning plans, which differ according to the canton of origin.

The ISOS surveys are published in book form and made available as PDF documents on the federal geoportal (Fig. 7).

¹³ ISOS Federal inventory on [opendata.swiss](https://opendata.swiss/it/dataset/bundesinventar-der-schutzenswerten-ortsbilder-der-schweiz-von-nationaler-bedeutung-isos), the national portal for publishing opendata :
<https://opendata.swiss/it/dataset/bundesinventar-der-schutzenswerten-ortsbilder-der-schweiz-von-nationaler-bedeutung-isos>

Figura 7 ISOS inventory map on the confederation portal. map.geo.admin.ch *Inventario federale ISOS*

Inventory of historic traffic routes in Switzerland (IVS)

The aim of the IVS inventory of historic transport routes is to protect Switzerland's historic transport routes. The IVS consists of two parts: the federal inventory and the remaining historic transport routes. Objects of national importance with obvious historical substance make up the federal inventory (approx. 3750 km) and enjoy special protection. The second part of the inventory consists of historic transport routes not included in the federal inventory, either of importance (e.g. for transport history) but with little or no historical substance (approx. 6800 km), or of regional importance (approx. 11500 km) or local importance (estimated at approx. 25000 km)¹⁴.

Table 1 Illustrative table of objects inscribed in the IVS

IVS – Inventory map	Classification	Characteristics
Federal inventory objects	Objects of national importance in accordance with Art. 3 and 4 OPVS (approx. 3,750 km).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enjoy special protection • Historic route with a lot of substance • Historic route with substance

¹⁴ List of objects of national importance. Ordinance on the Federal Inventory of Historic Swiss Traffic Routes (OPVS): https://www.ivs.admin.ch/images/bundesinventar/daten/PDF/2010_02_10_Streckenliste.pdf

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historic roads, streets and waterways (not the railways, tramways and cable cars of the past) • Distinct from archaeology
Historic routes included in the IVS	Objects of national importance but of which only the historical route is visible (about 6 800 km)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National importance according to historical context • Historical background of moderate or no substance
	Objects of regional importance according to Art. 11 OPVS (approx. 11,500 km)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical track with a lot of substance • Historic route with substance • Historic route
	Objects of local importance according to Art. 11 OPVS (approx. 25,000 km)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical track with a lot of substance • Historical track with substance • Historical track

The Federal Roads Office (USTRA) is the federal agency responsible for the inventory, which is responsible for monitoring, the payment of federal subsidies and the publication of specialised information. Unlike ISOS, it is the cantons that are responsible for the registration, designation, publication and protection of objects of regional and local significance. All inventory data can be downloaded or analysed using the WebSIG application (Fig. 8).

SIG IVS is Switzerland's official geo-information system, a multimedia map of Switzerland's historic transport routes. All detailed information on the IVS, which is not published in the official collection due to the size of the inventory (e.g. route, status, structural values and historical significance of the inventory), can be accessed and downloaded. Bibliographic data on route descriptions in the IVS GIS are available online and downloadable in text format¹⁵. The various search functions available allow the search of IVS objects according to both geographical and thematic criteria.

¹⁵ <https://www.ivs.admin.ch/it/servizio/download-e-ordinazioni>

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Figura 8 IVS inventory map on the confederation portal. <http://ivs-gis.admin.ch>.

The IVS consists of:

- **List of objects of national importance** with historical significance or extraordinary substance. They are classified in hierarchical order according to canton, route and segment¹⁶;
- **Inventory map.** Classification of historic routes at a scale of 1:25,000, representing their historical importance, indicating the "substance", i.e. the qualitative value of the construction and historical elements (shape, surface, boundaries and degree of preservation) and classifying them as "historic route with a lot of substance", "historic route with substance" or "historic route without substance" depending on the amount of traditional substance still visible in the terrain;
- **Topographic map.** The topographic map shows the main constructional and cultural-historical elements of the routes at the time of the survey (e.g. type of surface and boundaries, such as dry stone walls or rows of trees) at a scale of 1:25,000;

¹⁶ List of objects of national importance are also available in .pdf format at the link:
https://www.ivs.admin.ch/images/bundesinventar/daten/PDF/2010_02_10_Streckenliste.pdf

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- **Description of objects of national importance.** Detailed documentation with photographs, history of the object, constructional and territorial elements available for each historical route of national importance;
- **Objects of regional and local importance.** The IVS only provides information on objects classified by the cantons as being of regional or local importance, but the detailed documentation is collected in inventories drawn up and published by the cantons.

Federal Inventory of Landscapes and Natural Monuments (IFP)

Figura 9 Paesaggio lacustre dell'Alta Engadina, Lago di Sils (2015). Author: Luca Casartelli. CC-BY-SA. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Panorama_lago_di_Sils.jpg?uselang=it

The Federal Inventory of Landscapes and Natural Monuments (IFP) indicates the most valuable Swiss landscapes and natural monuments that should be preserved because of the diversity and uniqueness of the national geotopes. The IFP is managed by the Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) on behalf of the Federal Council, which is responsible for documenting and illustrating in detail the specific characteristics of the landscapes and for setting protection targets in cooperation with the cantons.

The IFP currently includes 162 objects of national importance (around 19% of Switzerland) which are divided into four typologies (Table 2):

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Table 2 Illustrative table of object included in the IFP

Typology	Description	Examples
Unique landscapes	Objects unique for their beauty, singularity, scientific, ecological or geographical-cultural importance	Bernese Alps, Rhine Falls, south shore of Lake Neuchâtel, Verzasca Valley and Creux-du-Van with the Areuse Gorges
Typical Swiss landscapes	Near-natural landscapes with a particularly characteristic morphology of the territory for a given region, cultural and historical evidence and important habitats for flora and fauna.	Chasseral, the Aargau and Solothurn Jura folds and the Belchen-Passwang region
Large-scale recreational landscapes	Landscapes that contribute significantly to people's psychological and physical well-being and to the formation of an identity bond with the territory.	Upper Engadin lake landscape and the Bernina range, the Emmental landscape and the Säntis region
Natural sites and monuments	Individual objects of biotic or abiotic nature such as erratic boulders, significant rock outcrops and characteristic landscape forms	Pflugstein above Herrliberg, the Lochsiten near Schwanden (Glarus overthrust), the Luegiboden block, the Euseigne pyramids and the glacier garden in Lucerne.

The inclusion of Swiss landscapes in the Inventory provides greater legal certainty in the management of Switzerland's natural and cultural heritage and in land-use planning and development by compensating for the limited compulsory nature of landscape and living space protection provisions. The aim of the IFP is to conserve natural resources, man-made landscapes and scenic beauty, to safeguard biodiversity in Switzerland, to promote quality of life and health, and to support the economy, particularly with regard to tourism and the attractiveness of Switzerland as a business location.

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Figura 10 IVS inventory map on the confederation portal. https://map.geo.admin.ch/?topic=bafu&lang=it&bgLayer=ch.swisstopo.pixelkarte-grau&catalogNodes=766&layers=ch.bafu.bundesinventare-bl&layers_opacity=0.75

Swiss heritage inventory of Unesco

Switzerland has 12 sites on the UNESCO World Heritage List, nine of which are cultural heritage and three natural heritage sites. These are:

1. **Old City of Berne** since 1983. Canton Bern. Cultural heritage site
1. **Convent of St Gall** since 1983. Canton St Gallen. Cultural heritage site
2. **Benedictine Convent of St John at Müstair** since 1983. Canton Grison. Cultural heritage site
3. **Three Castles, Defensive Wall and Ramparts of the Market-Town of Bellinzona** since 2000. Canton Ticino. Cultural heritage site
4. **Swiss Alps Jungfrau-Aletsch** since 2001. Cantons Bern and Valais. Natural heritage site
5. **Monte San Giorgio** (transnational site shared with Italy) since 2003. Canton Ticino. Natural heritage site
6. **Lavaux, Vineyard Terraces** since 2007. Canton Vaud. Cultural heritage site

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7. **Rhaetian Railway in the Albula / Bernina Landscapes** (transnational site shared with France) since 2008. Canton Grisons. Cultural heritage site
8. **Swiss Tectonic Arena Sardona** since 2008. Cantons Grisons, Glarus, St. Gallen. Natural heritage site
9. **La Chaux-de-Fonds / Le Locle** since 2009. Canton Neuchâtel. Cultural heritage sites.
10. **Prehistoric pile dwellings around the Alps** (transnational site shared with Austria, France, Germany, Italy, Slovenia) since 2011. On 111 locations, Switzerland host 56 sites. Cultural heritage sites.
11. **The Architectural Work of Le Corbusier, an Outstanding Contribution to the Modern Movement** (transnational site shared with Argentina, Belgium, France, Germany, India, and Japan) since 2016. Cantons Vaud and Geneve. Cultural heritage sites.

In addition as of 2020, Switzerland had two sites on its tentative list:

- Salginatobel Bridge, since 2017. Canton Grisons. Cultural heritage site.
- Ancient and Primeval Beech Forests of the Carpathians and Other Regions of Europe, since 2018. Canton Ticino and Solothurn. Natural heritage site

UNESCO cultural heritage sites are included in the PCP inventory with reference to individual buildings, as assets to be protected in the event of armed conflict and catastrophe, while UNESCO natural sites are not included as they do not fall within the scope of the inventory.

The protection of World Heritage in Switzerland is a function that is shared between several bodies. The Swiss UNESCO Commission acts as an interface between the state, civil society and UNESCO. In particular, it is responsible for coordinating the network of actors involved in the protection and promotion of World Heritage, for organising World Heritage sites as a whole and redirecting action where necessary, and for raising awareness in civil society of UNESCO's fundamental values, including intercultural dialogue, respect for the environment and sustainable development. At the federal level, the Federal Office for Culture and the Federal Office for the Environment are the competent authorities for the accompaniment and scientific support of World Heritage properties, while the Federal Department of Foreign Affairs (FDFA), UNESCO Section, is in charge of institutional relations at the international level.

Data on UNESCO natural and cultural heritage sites are also represented on the conference portal (Fig. 11).

For the admission of a site to the UNESCO World Heritage List, the government prepares a tentative list. The decision on acceptance is made by the UNESCO World Heritage Committee, supported by three expert advisory panels, the International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS), the International Centre for the Study of the Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Property (ICCROM) and the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN).

The criteria for the final selection are set out in the Convention, and relate to the outstanding universal value of a cultural or natural heritage, uniqueness, authenticity (historical truth) and integrity (wholeness) of the sites.

Figura 11 Mappa Inventario UNESCO sul portale della confederazione. https://map.geo.admin.ch/?topic=bafu&lang=it&bgLayer=ch.swisstopo.pixelkarte-grau&catalogNodes=766&layers=ch.bafu.bund.esinventare-blh.ch.bak.schutzgebiete-unesco_weltkulturerbe.ch.bafu.unesco-weltnaturerbe&layers_opacity=0.75,0.75,0.75&layers_visibility=false,true,true

Inventories of the Federal Department of Defence, Civil Protection and Sport (DDPS)

There are three other national inventories compiled by the DDPS on the basis of the LPN Act that were used, even minimally, for the classification of objects of national importance within the framework of the revised PCP inventory. This is because on the basis of international provisions

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(AIA Convention and the Second Protocol), the use of cultural property for military purposes is prohibited, although immunity from prosecution in the event of armed conflict cannot be guaranteed. According to the Swiss army's national legislation, military installations and constructions are prohibited within 500m of cultural property.

These are specifically:

1. **Inventory of military buildings with architectural value (HOBIM).** Some objects contained in the inventory, e.g. arsenals, barracks, can be listed as individual buildings, for which the usual PCP measures apply (against fire, flooding, natural hazards, etc.).
2. **Inventory of combat and conduct works worthy of conservation (ADAB).** These are aerial objects that are still used for military purposes and for which protection in the event of armed conflict cannot be guaranteed. Therefore, they are very rarely and only in exceptional cases (e.g. old army fortifications) considered for inclusion in the PCP Inventory.
3. **Inventory of combat and conduct works with ecological value or potential (IKFÖB).** This inventory is important above all for nature conservation and ecology and is not part of the aims of the PCP Inventory.

Other inventories used to define the Swiss Inventory of Cultural Property

There are other, more specific inventories (e.g. internal lists, national and official publications, inventories and catalogues) that have been consulted by the Confederation for the definition of cultural assets of national importance to be protected and included in the PCP inventory. These include

- List of architectural monuments protected by the Confederation
- SBB station lists
- Lists of customs and post office buildings
- Monuments of art and history of Switzerland
- Art guide of Switzerland
- Swiss Architecture Inventory 1850-1920 (INSA)
- Architectural Dictionary of Switzerland
- Guide to Swiss architecture 1920-1990
- Map of the castles of Switzerland
- ICOMOS list of historic gardens and parks in Switzerland
- Historical Dictionary of Switzerland (DSS)

Institutional regional scale inventory of Canton Ticino

The Office for Cultural Heritage (UBC), the Office for Civil Protection and Integrated Defence and the Civil Protection Regions (PCI) collaborate in the following activities:

- Training for the protection of cultural property (annual cantonal PCP course and repetition courses 6 PCP regions);
- Consulting in the drafting of the Swiss Inventory;
- Cantonal PCP working group;
- Liaison with the Federal Office for Civil Protection (FOCP) and the Federal Commission for the Protection of Cultural Property (FCPC);
- Preparation of handbooks and guidelines;
- Updating, in collaboration with the Information Systems Centre (ISC), of the functions of the Cultural Property Information System (SIBC) required by the Civil Protection Department.
- Management and use of photographs by third parties
- Consulting in the field of legislation

Collaboration between the Office for Cultural Heritage, the Cantonal Civil Defence Service and the individual Regions was developed especially in the area of cataloguing.

Until 1997, cataloguing was carried out by the OSMA (Swiss Society for Art Monuments) and the Cantonal Commission for Historical Monuments, which published the inventories for the Tre Valli, Bellinzona and district, Mendrisiotto and part of the Locarno area. In 1997, the Inventory Service of the Office for Cultural Heritage was created, which devised the Cultural Heritage Information System (SIBC) of Canton Ticino.

The inventory is the systematic collection (census) of all information on cultural properties that are protected under the regional law of the protection of cultural heritage (LBC, 1997) of cantonal and local importance and that have to be protected in the event of armed conflict or disaster. The inventory includes comparable information and essential data about the location, date of construction/execution, author, state of preservation, etc..

In 2002 Canton Ticino approved a message enabling the creation of an information data management system of the inventory, the SIBC (information system of cultural heritage).

The aims of the SIBC was to include in a single georeferenced database all the administrative, territorial, historical, artistic information (published and unpublished) related to movable and immovable cultural heritage including data by the Civil Protection (category of protection, measurements and weight of objects, intervention priorities, etc.). The SIBC also allowed

highlighting where information was missing, allowing new data collection processes and the activation of specific collaborations to complete the whole inventory. Finally the SIBC is connected with the databases of other administrative operating systems active such as the Land Registry which ensures the constant and direct updating of information related to the ownership of individual assets.

The SIBC is composed of four interacting components:

1. the database, with administrative, geographical and descriptive information;
2. the application, allowing operators to collect and manage information and to link them with other administrative operating systems;
3. the information system of the territory (SIT-TI) where geodata of movable and immovable cultural converged in order to research, analyses, represente and evaluate the numerical consistency and geographical spread of the heritage;
4. print production and data extraction of the database that may be passed on to third parties.

From 2005 (the year in which the SIBC went into production) to 2020, 137.169 objects have been cataloged, corresponding to 107.246 sheets (Fig. 12), divided into the following categories:

- Sheet A: Architecture = churches, buildings, architectural artifacts, gardens, bridges, etc.
- Sheet PA: Architectural part = bell towers, apses, halls, etc.
- Sheet OA: Work of art = paintings, sculptures, ecclesiastical grave goods, etc.
- Sheet C: Complex = groups of A
- Sheet I: Settlement = nucleus
- PRisp form: Perimeter of respect
- Sheet ZA: Area of archaeological interest

	A	C	I	OA	PAe	PAi	PRi	ZA	Conteggio
CDE	1574			1821		496			3891
RPCi1	19			9172		291			9482
RPCi2	17			3944		148			4109
RPCi3	10			16100		179			16289
RPCi4	173			7442		360			7975
RPCi5	8			11068		256			11332
RPCi6	87			10089		381			10557
UBC-Mandatario	13245		206	1588		1439			16478
UBC-SA	2								2
UBC-SI	12633	881	616	5806	487	5056	308	354	27131
Totale	27768	881	822	67030	487	9506	308	354	107246

Figura 12 Synthesis of the objects catalogued and the responsibilities of stakeholders involved.

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Today the cultural properties to be protected in Ticino in the event of armed conflict and natural catastrophe are 4.769, of which: 641 objects of national importance and 9 archaeological sites (Objects A); 514 objects of cantonal importance (Objects B) and 3605 of local importance (Objects C).

However the SIBC catalogue is not fully available to the public. This is because much of the information it includes, in particular those produced by the civil protections aiming at prioritizing intervention, defining the category of protection, the details and measures that should be taken into account when the rescues take place, etc, are strictly protected and cannot be authorized for public disseminations as their availability could have repercussions on cultural heritage security and generate targeted thefts.

Nevertheless, on the website of the canton of Ticino¹⁷ it is possible to consult the list of movable and immovable objects of cantonal and local importance protected under the LBC law (1997) and divided by municipality. This list contains basic information such as: the name of the object, type, location, fund number within the Land Registry, and often additional information such as photographs and technical descriptions.

Conclusions

Cultural heritage protection in Switzerland is organized as a federal system and it includes different national catalogues of heritage properties, sites and objects to be protected in case of natural disasters. This results in a very organized system with defined responsibilities and roles referring to the national, regional and local administrative levels.

As regards the Ticino case, the indications and inventories of the confederation are integrated into the regional laws and regulations, and since 2002 Canton Ticino has built and managed a strict cooperation with civil protection in order to guarantee the creation of the regional cultural heritage inventory and the protection of its related assets and objects.

Although the civil protection and the Cultural Heritage Office of Canton Ticino are well tuned in the realization of the inventory and on the procedures to be adopted to protect the heritage, the CHEERS project highlighted the importance to involve more the owners of properties and local stakeholders in the process of evaluation of objects to be protected.

Very often it happens that the owners of cultural heritage are completely unaware of the criteria for selecting, cataloging and prioritizing interventions about their movable objects (done by the experts of the cultural heritage office). Greater involvement of local stakeholders would make it possible to

¹⁷ <https://www4.ti.ch/dt/dstm/sst/ubc/temi/inventario-dei-beni-culturali/consultazione/consultazione/>

improve and make more effective the data collection and the evaluation system of the works to be safeguarded in the event of a natural disaster. Today this documentation is kept exclusively by the cultural heritage office, available and accessible in case of emergency for civil protection.

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